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DEVELOPMENT OF THE NON-OIL SECTOR IN AZERBAIJAN AND ITS ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

The article focuses on the issues of economic innovation, application of elements of knowledge economy and implementation of measures to update the criteria of economic development, the structure of the non-oil sector, accelerated structural changes and more serious state support to stimulate the development of export-oriented national economies. Expansion of non-oil export areas, strengthening the development of industries, support for national export companies, the introduction of a number of government mechanisms for the development of export and processing industries, strong state support for the ICT sector.

It is very important to implement a number of priorities and strategic goals in order to effectively use the export potential of the non-oil sector in accordance with successful reforms in Azerbaijan. Measures need to be taken to reduce resources, update the terms of trade, improve export incentives, conduct investment policies and improve the business environment that increase export potential, diversify the export structure and modernize export infrastructure.

Keywords: export potential, structure of import and export, regulation of export potential, non-oil industry.

Introduction: In modern conditions, a number of problems remain in the organization of the use of export potential in the non-oil sector in Azerbaijan:

1. First of all, along with oil and gas raw materials in the country, it is necessary to organize the processes of efficient development, production, processing of other natural resources and assess their export potential.

2. It is very important to ensure a systematic approach to the cycle of planning, production of non-oil export products, meeting export criteria and ensuring sustainable exports in foreign markets, and clearly defining goals in advance. [5]

Judging by the research materials on the development trends and diversification of the Azerbaijani economy, the significant decline in exports in Azerbaijan in 2019-2021 during the pandemic is a matter of serious concern. As this decrease is directly related to the decline in crude oil exports, we note that the expansion of the structure of non-oil exports is the most important strategic task facing our country in the coming years. Despite the development of the non-oil sector at the expense of oil revenues and the strengthening of its export potential, and the large-scale organization of government mechanisms, the export potential of the non-oil sector does not reflect the current situation in the country. [4]

Azerbaijan has rich resources, favorable geographical location, industrial and agricultural sectors with strong export potential. The creation of a network of competitive industrial enterprises on the basis of new equipment and technologies is characterized as an important condition for their effective use. In addition, in the near future to increase the competitiveness of the economy, create a developed market infrastructure, create public financial institutions that can accelerate the diversification of the economy, intensify economic innovation processes, oil and gas engineering, petrochemistry, metallurgy, construction materials, agrarian sector and agriculture. Ensuring the development of the

ICT sector, tourism and the realization of the maximum use of the export potential of the space industry are expected to be addressed as important tasks. [7]

If measures to increase the range of competitive and export-oriented products in the non-oil sector of the country, especially in the industrial sector, do not lead to a significant increase from the current level, it is unlikely to achieve significant growth in the country's industrial potential and non-oil sector. To this end, the organization of production and export of export-oriented products with significant potential to individual non-oil sectors should be carefully studied, the application of world experience should be given wide coverage, and more effective mechanisms for the country's foreign trade concept should be developed.

Research shows that the effective organization of foreign trade and the strengthening of export potential are important factors in ensuring the sustainable development of the national economy. Thus, foreign trade provides access to international markets for economic and business entities, accelerates the exchange of goods and technologies between countries, introduces new technologies, modern equipment and advanced management methods to the production, economic and management spheres of the national economy. It enhances the country's image in the international arena, strengthens its position in world commodity markets, increases the country's foreign exchange resources, stimulates the diversification of the national economy, and creates favorable conditions for its diversification. [6]

If we look at the existing facts, we can see that some progress has been made in the development of the non-oil sector in the Azerbaijani economy recently. In 2020, 50,792.5 million manat of value added was created in the non-oil sector of the economy in Azerbaijan. The share of value added in the non-oil sector in GDP was 70.1%.

In 2020, the share of trade and vehicle repair in the

non-oil sector will be 16.4%, construction 11%, transport and warehousing 10.1%, agriculture, forestry and fisheries 9.9%, non-oil industry 7.5%. [8]

The growth rate of value added created in most areas of the non-oil sector was higher than in the corresponding period of the previous year.

Compared to the corresponding period of 2019, there was an increase of 12% in non-oil industry, 4.6% in transport and warehousing, 1.9% in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, 0.6% in information and communication.

In 2020, the non-oil industry produced goods worth 11,681 million manat, and production increased by 12.5% compared to the same period last year.

The share of mining industry in the production of non-oil industry is 3.9% or 450.4 million manat, the share of processing industry is 76.5% or 8937.6 million manat, the share of production, distribution and supply of electricity, gas and steam is 16.9% or 1974.4 million manat, and the share of water supply and waste treatment was 2.7% or 318.6 million manat.

Compared to the same period last year, production in 2020 in most sectors of the non-oil refining industry, including the textile industry (7.4%), clothing (32.7%), leather and leather products, footwear (4, 7%), processing of wood and wood products other than furniture (67.4%), production of paper and cardboard (36.9%), chemical industry (20.5%), production of pharmaceuticals (10.7 d.), in the production of rubber and plastic products (13.5%), in the metallurgical industry (11.9%), in the production of computer, electronic and optical products (34.5%), in the production of automobiles, trailers and semi-trailers (35.7%), production of other vehicles (47%), etc. increased in areas.

The value of gross agricultural output in actual prices, which is one of the main areas of the non-oil sector, amounted to 8,428.9 million manat, of which 4,400.5 million manat fell to livestock and 4,028.4 million manat to crop production.

Recently, the construction industry in the country is developing rapidly. In 2020, 17028.1 million manat or 8.3 percent less than the previous year was directed to fixed assets from all financial sources for the development of economic and social spheres of the country.

The volume of value added created in the non-oil industry in the country in 2020 increased by 12% compared to the same period last year and reached 3822.9 million manat. In the structure of value added in the non-oil industry, the share of the mining industry is 4%, the share of the processing industry is 72.1%, the share of electricity, gas and steam production, distribution and supply is 20.2%, the share of water supply and waste treatment It was 3.7%.

The volume of investments in the oil and gas sector increased by 0.3%, while the volume of funds directed to the non-oil and gas sector decreased by 12.3%. 11175.8 million manat or 65.6% of the total investment fell to the share of production areas, 4485.0 million manat (26.4%) to service areas, and 1367.3 million manat (8.0%) to the construction of residential houses.

41.6% of the total investment was made by state and 58.4% by private sector investors. 64.3% of investments were spent on construction and installation works.

The value of funds directed to fixed capital from domestic sources was 69.9% of the total investment.

Despite the current pandemic conditions in the country, in 2020, DOST Center No. 3 in Baku, "Boyukshor" and "Ahmadli" power substations, a factory for the production of protective overalls, a plant for the production of construction materials in Ganja, "Asan Hayat" complex in Agjabadi district, processing plant, branch of "Azerkhalcha" OJSC in Astara region, Agrarian Industrial Complex, regional "Asan service" center in Balakan region, branch of "Azerkhalcha" OJSC in Goranboy region, "Asan Hayat" complex in Kurdamir region, "Azerkhalcha" OJSC branch, lime plant in Gazakh region, Museum of State Symbols in Tartar region, branch of "Azerkhalcha" OJSC, "Asan Hayat" complex in Tovuz region, branch of "Azerkhalcha" OJSC, Museum of State Symbols, "Shamkirchay" Water Treatment Plant Complex in Shamkir region and s. was opened up; activated.

It should be noted that cargo and passenger traffic due to coronavirus (COVID-19) infection (hereinafter pandemic) in 2020 decreased by 19.8 percent and 42.7 percent, respectively, compared to the previous year.

In 2020, the carriers served 1 177.6 million passengers. 93.4% of passengers were transported by road, 6.3% by subway, and the rest by other modes of transport.

According to the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the value added in the field of tourist accommodation and catering in January-September 2020 amounted to 821.1 million manat, and the share of this sector in non-oil GDP was 1.6 percent.

As a result of the crisis caused by the pandemic, the decline in the tourism sector has been observed in Azerbaijan, as in other countries. According to the State Border Service, in 2020, 795.7 thousand foreigners and stateless persons came to Azerbaijan from 155 countries, or 4.0 times less than in 2019.

In 2020, 28.3 percent of visitors will come from the Russian Federation, 23.2 percent from Georgia, 20.2 percent from Turkey, 9.1 percent from Iran, 2.1 percent from Ukraine, 1.6 percent from India, 1.5 percent from Saudi Arabia. Kazakhstan with 1.1 percent, Pakistan, the United Arab Emirates and Turkmenistan with 1.0 percent each, Kuwait and the United Kingdom with 0.9 percent each, Belarus with 0.8 percent, Uzbekistan and Iraq with 0.7 percent each. 0.5 percent were citizens of Israel, 0.4 percent of each were Germany and Italy, 4.5 percent were citizens of other countries, and 0.1 percent were stateless persons.

At present, the main task ahead is to achieve an increase in exports in the non-oil sector. Thus, in 2020, Azerbaijan's total exports amounted to 13.7 billion US dollars, and in the non-oil sector - 1.9 billion US dollars. Exports in the non-oil sector decreased by 102 million US dollars or 5.2% compared to 2019. Thus, in 2020, 691 million to Russia, 377.8 million to Turkey, 224.8 million to Switzerland, 127 to Georgia, Non-oil goods worth \$ 6 million and \$ 44.5 million were exported to China.

In the list of non-oil exports in 2020, gold (\$ 205.6 million) is first, tomatoes (\$ 201.4 million) is second, and cottonseed (\$ 131.9 million) is third. [8]

Despite the damage caused by COVID-19, the non-oil industry has developed in the country. On January 6 this year, a video conference on the results of 2020 was held under the chairmanship of President Ilham Aliyev. At the meeting, the President said that our non-oil industry has grown by more than 11 percent. At the expense of what? Exactly at the expense of diversification. Because the policy of industrialization was carried out correctly. [1]

It should be noted that the development of the non-oil sector is a priority of the Azerbaijani economy. This is confirmed in the Strategic Roadmap for the national economy and its key sectors, approved by Presidential Decree dated December 6, 2016. [2]

The development of the non-oil sector has also been a priority in the state programs adopted consistently (4 programs). The share of the non-oil sector in GDP has increased significantly and new jobs have been created. [3]

Despite the war and the fight against the pandemic to liberate the occupied territories from Armenia in 2020, the share of the non-oil sector in our country has not decreased. Thus, last year the GDP was about 72.5

billion manat, of which 50 billion 792.5 million manat was in the non-oil sector.

As a result of successful reforms in the country, successful implementation of the Strategic Road Map has led to macroeconomic stability, growth of the non-oil sector and exports, improved trade and fiscal balance, favorable business environment and investment, sustainable infrastructure improvement and social welfare, as well as strengthening international relations. .

Research shows that it will further increase the competitiveness, inclusion and social welfare of the economy, attract investment, create a free competitive environment, expand market access and promote human capital development. It is planned to further strengthen the position of our country in the world economy and join the group of high-income countries. It should be noted that the non-oil sector plays a crucial role in job creation and has a positive impact on both economic and social development.

The experience of other countries shows that today the transition of national economies to a model of sustainable development is crucially related to the volume and quality of human capital. The development of ICT and the financial and banking sector is also in focus. The development of logistics and trade is also a priority in the Strategic Road Map.

As a result of the study, we conclude that the potential to increase the production of many competitive agricultural and agrarian sectors in Azerbaijan is poorly used. Noting the poor use of the potential to increase the export of a group of agricultural and agrarian sector products (fresh vegetables, fresh fruits, potatoes, tea, fats and oils, grape wine, vegetable oils, etc.), which currently have favorable conditions for cultivation, storage and export in Azerbaijan can be done. The problems of more objective assessment of export potential and identification of effective export directions in this area remain unresolved.

In addition, extensive work has been done over the past 18 years to strengthen and improve the legal framework for regulating the export potential of the non-oil sector. Presidential decrees and orders were issued, laws were adopted, state programs, concepts and strategies were approved in order to regulate export operations, stimulate exports, develop entrepreneurship and improve the business environment, strengthen economic activity in the regions, and accelerate the development of individual sectors with sufficient export potential. has been. At the same time, it can be concluded that there is a need to adopt more sustainable, efficient, reliable and perfect laws to stimulate the country's exports, especially non-oil exports. In the process of drafting and adopting such laws and export regulations, the expansion of foreign economic relations in the direction of non-oil exports, stimulating access of non-oil sector entities to international markets, simplification of export procedures, promotion of export operations, barriers to improving investment investment policy Consideration of important factors such as restriction should be kept in focus.

We have come to the conclusion that in modern times it is important to increase the export potential of Azerbaijan, especially non-oil exports. This is due to

the fact that goods and products that do not have competitiveness and specialization in international markets have limited opportunities to strengthen in export markets. Therefore, our conclusion is that in the global economic environment, Azerbaijan should take advantage of the financial opportunities provided by the export of crude oil and natural gas and create the potential to export a wide range of non-oil goods based on the criteria of sustainability and competitiveness. In other words, the principle of "optimal balance of hydrocarbon and non-hydrocarbon exports is an important condition in the development of an export strategy" must be taken into account.

RESULTS AND SUGGESTIONS

To this end, the multi-vector nature of ways to expand the export potential of Azerbaijan's non-oil sector should be taken as a key priority:

1. On the basis of modern criteria for diversification of the national economy, export-oriented sectors of the economy should be taken as a priority.

2. Multifunctional regulation and improvement mechanisms that can mobilize export potential should be developed and applied, taking into account modern development trends of the country's economy, specific features of world commodity markets, global economic development processes and the impact of economic transformations.

3. Natural and economic factors with prospects for participation in increasing the export potential of the non-oil sector in Azerbaijan should be studied in depth, and on this basis, measures to expand the production of non-oil export products capable of effective results should be strengthened.

4. The export potential of each of the non-oil sectors of the country, including the modern economy (ICT, tourism, space industry, etc.) should be objectively assessed and forecasted at least until 2030.

5. There is a need to update and increase the efficiency of government mechanisms to support the export potential of the non-oil sector in Azerbaijan.

6. In order to increase the export potential of the country's non-oil sector, a state policy on attracting more modern and targeted foreign investments should be formed, and mechanisms for optimal management of the processes of attracting, directing and efficient use of these investments should be developed.

Finally, taking into account the importance of the export potential of the non-oil sector in increasing the resilience of the country's economy, in order to ensure the integrated development of this sector, Azerbaijan 2030: National Socio-Economic Development Priorities It is very important to develop large international projects, establish international companies, expand relations with countries around the world to strengthen the country's export potential products in world markets, and further strengthen the active use of these relations in measures to increase export potential.

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